

MEDICAL DISCOURSE AND ITS COMMUNICATIVE SPECIFICITY

Babajanov Khudaynazar Rajapovich

TMA Urgench branch, assistant professor, PhD

Sapaeva Dilfuza Narbaevna

TMA Urgench branch, Department of English language,

assistant professor, PhD

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Abstract. *Medical discourse studies communicative activities related to the topic of life and health of people, and deserves special attention from the point of view of anthropocentric and functional linguistic approaches, since the analysis of various types of linguistic interactions covers both professional communication between specialists and the interaction of a specialist and a patient, while the latter is at the same time the main object and subject of medical care. In this article, the problem of researching professional discourse is closely related to the process of multilevel research of English for specific purposes within the framework of the cognitive-linguistic approach.*

Keywords: *medical discourse, professional speech, cognitive linguistics, anthropocentrism, lexicography, conceptual metaphor.*

МЕДИЦИНСКИЙ ДИСКУРС И ЕГО КОММУНИКАТИВНАЯ СПЕЦИФИКА

Аннотация. *Медицинский дискурс изучает коммуникативную деятельность, касающуюся темы жизни и здоровья людей, и заслуживает особого внимания с точки зрения антропоцентрического и функционального лингвистического подходов, поскольку анализ различных видов языковых взаимодействий охватывает как профессиональное общение между специалистами, так и взаимодействие специалиста и пациента, при этом, последний является одновременно основным объектом и субъектом медицинской помощи. В этой статье изучена проблема исследования профессионального дискурса тесно связана с процессом многоуровневого исследования английского языка для специальных целей в рамках когнитивно-лингвистического подхода.*

Ключевые слова: *медицинский дискурс, профессиональная речь, когнитивная лингвистика, антропоцентризм, лексикография, концептуальная метафора.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, there is no single scientific position regarding the independence of the discipline called medical linguistics, however, some researchers talk about the need to separate it from the circle of linguistic sciences. This problem worries linguists of domestic and foreign linguistics.

The topicality of identifying and describing the linguistic and cultural specifics of a scientific text is due to a number of factors.

Literary review. scientific works of local and foreign linguists studying the problems of medical discourse (L.S. Beilinson, V.V. Zhura, E.A. Kostyashina, Yu.V. Rudova, S.V. Maiboroda, I.F. Shamara, K.A. Kerer, T.V. Kochetkova, M.I. Barsukova, E.A. Rempel, A.Ya. Ramazanova, S.I. Madzhaeva, L.M. Kasimtseva, etc.).

Taking into account the stylistic coloring in our materials, we can distinguish between official and unofficial etiquette formulas. When studying etiquette formulas in the doctor-patient communication system, we identified three aspects of their functioning in speech:

- 1) formulas for the beginning and end of the conversation (hello, goodbye);
- 2) maintaining a dialogue (please, thank you);
- 3) genre representation of the main groups of speech etiquette (request, advice, recommendation).

In the process of research, we have achieved certain results regarding the lexicographic representation of medical concepts in various types of dictionaries. It follows from the foregoing that, on the one hand, specialized terminological dictionaries represent medical terms in the traditional way, using a known range of linguistic means close to the presentation of a scientific text. At the same time, in some cases, comments are used to explain the meanings of the most complex facts, phenomena, processes and corresponding linguistic expressions. The algorithm for representing concepts related to certain diseases is based on the anthological unity of the fundamental concepts of the conceptual field of medicine, i.e. symptoms, causes, therapy, preventive measures.

Starting to communicate with the patient, the doctor must immediately establish contact with the patient, determine the general tone of the conversation. Units of speech etiquette help to establish favorable contact with the patient, arrange him for yourself, and maintain the desired tone of communication.

There are given some examples and to analyze how well-known medical concepts are presented in dictionaries. Take, for example, the word "headache". The Cambridge Dictionary for Advanced Learners presents this block as "a pain you feel inside your head: *I've got a headache*" literal and figurative "something that causes you great difficulty and worry:

Finding a babysitter for Saturday evening will be a major headache. [Cambridge Advanced Learner's Dictionary, 2005, pp. 590].

The Longman WordWise Dictionary contains the following definition: "a pain in your head", followed by the example "*I've got a terrible headache*" [Longman WordWise Dictionary, 2007, pp. 274]. The Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture defines "headache" in its direct meaning: "a pain in the head:

"I always get headaches after reading. I've got a bad headache"

And figuratively: "a difficult or worrying problem:

Trying to make the children eat is one big headache! [Longman Dictionary of English Language and Culture, 2008, pp. 644].

The dictionary of medical terms contains the following definition: "a pain in the head, caused by changes in pressure in the blood vessels feeding the brain which act on the nerves. Also called "*cephalalgia*" [Dictionary of Medical Terms, 2008, pp. 171]. Thus, despite the fact that one of the most important features of terms is their semantic uniqueness due to meaning and expression, the use of analogues of Latin or Greek origin is inherent in medical terminology. Another very important point is that a dictionary entry can often be accompanied by a comment that indicates the nature and types of the disease (in our case, a headache):

"Headaches can be caused by a blow to the head, by lack of sleep or food, by eye strain, sinus infections and many other causes. Mild headaches can be treated with analgesic and rest. Severe headaches which recur may be caused by serious disorders in the head or nervous system".

Cognitive metaphors can be used for communicative pragmatic purposes in medical discourse, including ethical issues of communication. At the same time, there are situations in

which the use of metaphors does not have any positive effect on patients and can be detrimental in the process of establishing mutual understanding between interlocutors. As already noted, a lot depends on discourse factors, which include such elements as language features, characteristics of the communication situation, conceptual and linguistic relationships of the communicant's worldview. Metaphors play an important role in some situations of decision-making using specific linguistic means, which are especially important from the point of view of medical communication.

CONCLUSION

Thus, a scientific medical text is characterized by specific functionality, communicative situation and content, i.e. has its own special criteria of textuality, is a product of the discursive activity of the author - a participant in a certain communicative situation and has the specifics of expressing the author's position, is fixed in writing, is characterized by a specific compositional-content and structural-speech organization and completeness, i.e. has its own functionality. All of the above gives reason to believe that the scientific medical text should be studied in the context of medical linguistics.

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